

Laojun Shan (Mountain of Lord Lao)

also known as “Tianshe Shan (Mt. Celestial Altar)”, “Chougeng Shan (Mt. Chougeng)”, “Chougeng Zhi (Chougeng Diocese)”

Data source: Mapping Religious Diversity in Modern Sichuan
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** Data Source entry, prepared based on data sourced from an external project.*

Entry tags: Liumen, China, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult, Sichuan, shrines, Monastery, Quanzhen, Daoism, Hill, Open-Air Sanctuary, Peak Sanctuaries, Chinese Religion, Monument, Temple, Religious Place, Religious Group, Religious Complex

The Mountain of Lord Lao (Laojun Shan 老君山) in Xinjin 新津 district, Sichuan 四川 province, has been identified as the center of a former diocese of Celestial Master Daoism (Tianshi Dao 天師道). Moreover, it is well-known as a sanctuary for the worship of Laozi 老子. The temple on Mt. Laojun is today an active religious institution that belongs to the Dragon Gate (Longmen 龍門) lineage of Complete Perfection (Quanzhen 全真) Daoism. In the late Qing dynasty and Republican times, the temple was closely connected with the influential Liu School (Liumen 劉門) tradition, which was founded by the Confucian scholar Liu Yuan 劉沅 (1768–1856). The district of Xinjin is located in the western part of the Sichuan basin, southwest of the provincial capital Chengdu 成都. About two kilometers south of the district town, the Mountain of Lord Lao (Laojun Shan) rises up amidst a ridge of hills, surrounded by the rivers Minjiang 岷江 and Nanhe 南河. Mt. Laojun, a cone-shaped hill, is only 617 meters high, but it figures prominently among the historic sites of Xinjin and remains a famous sanctuary for the worship of Lord Lao 老君, the deified Laozi. Although the traditional temple complex, hidden in a cypress grove on the summit, received its present shape only in the first half of the 20th century, the origins of this sacred site can be traced back to the very beginnings of the Daoist religion. “Laojun Shan” is actually a popular designation of the mountain, which only appeared in written sources as late as in the Qing dynasty (1644–1911). Two other appellations for this locality can be found in earlier historical and geographical treatises. The first of these, Tianshe Shan 天社山 (Mt. Celestial Altar), probably originated in the designation of a stellar constellation and refers to the ridge of hills south of the district town of Xinjin, of which Mt. Laojun forms a part. However, the name “Tianshe Shan” is still used as synonym for Laojun Shan today. The other appellation, Chougeng Shan 稠稷山 (Mt. Chougeng), matches the name of the old diocese in Daoist sources: Chougeng Zhi 稠稷治 or Chougeng Hua 稠稷化. The exact meaning of chougeng 稠稷 is not clear. The word seemingly designates a medicinal herb or a kind of rice. To my knowledge, the geographical name “Chougeng” only occurs at this locality in Xinjin and does not relate to any other place. Legend has it that Lord Lao once dwelled there in a cave and engaged in secluded self-cultivation. This legend is not supported by source texts in the Daoist Canon, but Lord Lao has nevertheless become the central deity who bestows spiritual authority upon the mountain, and the locality and its temple were consequently named after the God of the Dao. While Daozang 道藏 sources report that the Yellow Emperor (Huangdi 黃帝) and Celestial Master Zhang Daoling 張道陵 once stayed at Chougeng Diocese, the legend of Lord Lao’s sojourn on the mountain apparently is based on local lore. The sanctuary on top of the mountain, commonly referred to as Laojun Miao 老君廟 (Temple of Lord Lao) or Laozi Miao 老子廟 (Temple of Laozi), currently serves as residence for a community of Daoist clerics and lay adherents. Very little is known about the history of the temple. Summarizing the bits of information contained in a temple bell inscription dated 1796, historical treatises on geography, and local gazetteers, we learn that temple buildings were erected on the mountain starting in the Han (206 BCE–220 CE) and Tang (618–907) dynasties. In 1644, the temple was destroyed by troops of the rebel Zhang Xianzhong 張獻忠 (1606–1647), who set up a short-lived regime in Chengdu. The sanctuary finally underwent reconstruction in the last decade of the 18th century. In the late Qing dynasty and Republican times (1912–1949), the sanctuary on Mt.

Laojun was closely connected with the Liumen tradition. In 1799, 1821, and 1835, various temple buildings on Mt. Laojun were rebuilt or restored under the auspices of Liu Yuan, the founder and first patriarch of the Liumen tradition. Liu Yuan reportedly had spent some time on this mountain while studying meditation techniques under the guidance of a Daoist hermit, who was eventually considered an incarnation of Laozi in Liumen circles. Since Liumen adherents held Laozi in high esteem, they actively supported and patronized Daoist institutions, in particular those that were dedicated to the cult of Laozi. The extant temple buildings on Mt. Laojun were constructed during the Republican era, sponsored by local adherents of the Liumen community. After a devastating fire in 1923, Liu Xianjun 劉咸焯 (1871-1935), a grandson of Liu Yuan and the fourth patriarch of the Liumen movement, supervised the reconstruction of the sanctuary. The architectural ensemble was modelled on the famous Daoist temple Qingyang Gong 青羊宮 (Palace of the Grey Goat) in Chengdu, which was also patronized by the Liumen community. Beside the temple's main Hall of the Three Clarities (Sanqing Dian 三清殿), a modest shrine hall is situated, its front opening into a walled courtyard. The name of this building is Rulin Ci 儒林祠 (Ancestral Temple of the Literati), and it was erected in honor of Liu Yuan and his descendants. After the founding of the People's Republic of China (1949), the Liumen tradition was outlawed as a "reactionary secret society," and Mt. Laojun was consequently deprived of its former protectors. After the turmoil of the "Cultural Revolution" (1966-1976), the temple was finally reopened as a religious institution in 1986. While most of its traditional buildings and relics have been preserved, the temple complex on Mt. Laojun was extended by several new edifices in recent years.

Date Range: 142 CE - 2022 CE

Region: Laojun Shan, Xinjin, Sichuan

Region tags: China, Sichuan

Area of Mt. Laojun in Xinjin district, Chengdu, Sichuan (present)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Volker Olles, *Der Berg des Lao Zi in der Provinz Sichuan und die 24 Diözesen der daoistischen Religion*, Wiesbaden: Harrassowitz, 2005 (Asien- und Afrika-Studien der Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; 24), ISBN 3-447-05261-9.
- Source 2: Volker Olles, "The Gazetteer of Mt. Tianshe – How the Liumen Community Reshaped a Daoist Sacred Mountain," in: PHILIP CLART (ed.). *Chinese and European Perspectives on the Study of Chinese Popular Religions*. Taipei: Boyang wenhua, 2012, pp. 229–263. (See attached PDF file.)
- Source 3: Volker Olles, "Das Erbe des Himmelsmeisters: der 'Berg des Laojun' in der Provinz Sichuan und seine Bedeutung als daoistisches Heiligtum vom 2. Jahrhundert n. Chr. bis in die Gegenwart," in: *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Morgenländischen Gesellschaft* 150/1 (2000), pp. 269–297.
- Source 1: 欧福克 (Volker Olles), "Baohu dongtian fudi, jianli renjian xianjing – Sichuan Xinjin xian Laojun shan de lishi yu xianzhuang" 保护洞天福地, 建立人间仙境——四川新津县老君山的历史与现状, in: *Zhongguo Daojiao 中国道教 (China Taoism)* 4, 2007, p. 58.

- Source 2: Volker Olles, “Lord Lao’s Mountain: From Celestial Master Daoism to Contemporary Daoist Practice,” in: *Journal of Daoist Studies* 2 (2009), pp. 109–136.
- Source 3: 欧福克 (Volker Olles) , “Laozi yinju zhi suo: yi Tianshe shan zhi wei zhongxin de lishi dili kaocha” 老子隐居之所：以《天社山志》为中心的历史地理考察, translated by HU RUI 胡锐, in: *Zongjiaoxue yanjiu* 宗教学研究 (Religious Studies) 3, 2018, pp. 68–75. Reprinted in: *Zhongguo Renmin Daxue Fuyin baokan ziliao*. *Zongjiao* 中国人民大学复印报刊资料·宗教 1, 2019, pp. 86–94.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://720yun.com/t/favku78qg7w?scene_id=40727191
- Source 1 Description: Virtual tour of Mt. Laojun (in Chinese)
- Source 2 URL: <https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/22iVKrVttt4nQ04P4vGmLQ>
- Source 2 Description: Academic article by Volker Olles on the modern history of Mt. Laojun (in Chinese)
- Source 3 URL: <https://mp.weixin.qq.com/s/5M7E08seoaGHP-kHmMoPVg>
- Source 3 Description: TOC of the book "Der Berg des Lao Zi" by Volker Olles
- Source 1 URL: https://m.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_16254536
- Source 1 Description: Article about Mt. Laojun (part 1), written for a general audience by Volker Olles (in Chinese)
- Source 2 URL: [https://m.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_16373572?from=HOTQRcode&hotContIds=16405340,16378325,16405331,16403875,](https://m.thepaper.cn/newsDetail_forward_16373572?from=HOTQRcode&hotContIds=16405340,16378325,16405331,16403875)
- Source 2 Description: Article about Mt. Laojun (part 2), written for a general audience by Volker Olles (in Chinese)

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Illicit

Notes: Relics from the Han (206 BCE–220 CE) and Ming (1368–1644) dynasties were excavated on Mt. Laojun and in its surroundings during the Republican era (1912–1949).

Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1912–1949

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Various relics discovered by temple staff and tomb raiders

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Hill

– Tree, grove, or forest

– Water source

– Cave

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Notes: The traditional temple complex was built in accordance with the natural shape of Mt. Laojun and had very little impact on the original environment. However, a big new temple hall (Doumu Dian 斗姥殿) was erected behind the old temple in recent years, which is situated on a huge man-made terrace.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The original environs of Mt. Laojun are rural, but several quasi-urban structures have been built around the hill, e.g., a hotel, amusement parks etc. Furthermore, new residence areas have also been set up in the environs of Mt. Laojun. Thus, urbanization is proceeding, but it remains to be seen to what extent it will affect Mt. Laojun.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

- ↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:
 - Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:
– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

- ↳ A single structure
 - No

- ↳ One single feature
 - Purposefully placed plants

Notes: Cypresses planted during the Ming and Qing dynasties are still preserved on Mt. Laojun.

- ↳ A group of structures:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - Yes

- ↳ A group of features:
 - Yes

- ↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
 - No

- ↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
 - No

- ↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
 - Worship

↳ Worship:
–Other [specify]: communal and individual

– Social

– Memorial

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– Yes

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
– Burned

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
–For political reasons
–As the result of war
–Other [specify]: A fire in 1923 that destroyed most of the temple buildings was an accident. However, in 1644 the temple was devastated during war, and after 1949, especially during the "Cultural Revolution", parts of the temple complex and all statues were destroyed on purpose.

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
–Human-caused accident

Notes: A fire in 1923 was caused by bundles of firewood for the temple's kiln that were ignited by candles and firecrackers during a temple festival.

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– No

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: All common Daoist deities: Three Clarities 三清, Taishang Laojun 太上老君 (Laozi) as single deity, Three Officers 三官, Wang Lingguan 王靈官, Zhao Gongming 趙公明, Cihang Zhenren 慈航真人 (Guanyin), Wenchang 文昌, Guandi 關帝, Zhang Daoling 張道陵 etc. Furthermore, the Seven Patriarchs 七真 of Quanzhen Daoism, Twelve Gold Immortals 十二金仙, and the Patriarchs of the Liumen Tradition (not extant).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Notes: Liu Yuan 劉沅 and other patriarchs of the Liumen tradition were worshipped in the Rulin Ci (Ancestral Temple of the Literati) on Mt. Laojun, but this cult has not been continued by today's Quanzhen clerics.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: Mt. Laojun was identified as one of the 24 Dioceses 二十四治 of Celestial Master Daoism. According to various source texts in the Daoist Canon, the dioceses were revealed by the Most High Lord Lao (Taishang Laojun 太上老君) and put under the control of the first Celestial Master, Zhang Daoling 張道陵, in 142 or 143 CE (i.e., the first or second year of the Han'an 漢安 reign).

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Except from its early function as Celestial Masters' Diocese, Mt. Laojun was also

regarded as the retreat of Laozi, which is obviously based on local lore.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Originally, the buildings of the Qing dynasty temple on Mt. Laojun faced south (癸山丁向). Now, the temple halls of the new sanctuary, constructed under the aegis of the Liumen community in Republican times, were designed to face west (乙山辛向) in order to conform to the assumed meaning of a poem received through spirit-writing. This means that the orientation of the temple Laojun miao was rotated exactly ninety degrees. The Cavern of Lord Lao (Laojun dong 老君洞) underneath the summit is the spiritual heart of Mt. Laojun, since Laozi reportedly once stayed there and engaged in self-cultivation. This cavern and two adjacent cliff tombs all face west; it is indeed striking that the halls of the Laojun miao point in the same direction. The orientation of the temple halls obviously follows that of the caverns, which was hinted at in the revealed poem. Therefore, the whole temple complex was reconstructed according to natural features and the principles of fengshui that had been disclosed in a revelation.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The status of the buildings rises in an ascending order. The main halls housing statues of high divinities are located on the summit.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 30

Notes: This is a guess. Actually, like on other sacred mountains in China, a large part of the area will not be taken up by buildings, but remain untouched, often constituting a nature-sanctuary. However, since Mt. Laojun is rather small, the percentage of area covered with buildings is higher than that of other sacred mountains.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: The shape and footprint of all monuments on Mt. Laojun follow the natural features of the mountain. Some buildings are attached to others through courtyards, making it hard to assess its actual size. To provide a direct insight into the architecture of the Laojun Miao, I attach photographs and ground plans (the latter only pertaining to historical or rebuilt structures) of all major buildings on Mt. Laojun.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

Notes: There are certain features that imitate an ideal Daoist landscape.

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– I don't know

↳ Plaster
– I don't know

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: All traditional temple halls are built out of bricks and wooden components (pillars etc.).
Even the walls of the major sacred cavern (Laojun Dong), which is a natural cave, have been lined with bricks.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Wooden tablets with horizontal or vertical inscriptions are part of many entrance areas.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– I don't know

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Other types of decoration include stylized images of water, fire and religious emblems etc.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– Yes

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: none

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– I don't know

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Background reliefs are frequently found behind statues.

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Other [specify]: Most of the background paintings behind some statues are of modern and recent origin.

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– I don't know

Notes: If yes, then these paintings are of a very recent origin.

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– I don't know

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: The background paintings behind some statues mostly show woods,

landscapes, mythical animals like cranes etc.

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Poems and commemorative inscriptions on steles

↳ Other type of decoration:

– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– Yes

Notes: Some Thunder Deities and Celestial Master Zhang Daoling have a third (vertical) eye on their foreheads.

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Dragons and other mythical animals are part of the iconography.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– Yes

Notes: Most of the statues in the Laozi Miao display standard iconographic features of the Daoist and Buddhist traditions.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– I don't know

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: There are various depictions of Taiji (Yin-Yang), the eight trigrams and the 64 hexagrams of the Book of Changes (Yijing), the Chinese zodiac etc.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Some statues show ancestral masters (zushi 祖師) of the Daoist tradition who are historical persons.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

Notes: The group of the twelve Gold Immortals (jinxian 金仙) worshiped at side shrines in the Sanqing Dian derive from 16th-century Chinese novel The Investiture of the Gods (Fengshen Yanyi 封神演義).

↳ Human narratives

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Certain deities and cultural heroes are worshiped in the form of steles bearing only their names and titles.

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Graves (or grave clusters) of deceased Daoists and other people, who had a

personal connection to Mt. Laojun, are present in certain locations around the temple complex.

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: There is a huge number of deities in Daoism, many of whom are also worshiped on Mt. Laojun. Daoist deities include abstract (however, having a human form) representations of the Dao, stellar deities, deified masters, mythic culture heroes, cosmic and natural forces, exorcist protectors etc. All deities are ultimately viewed as emanations of the Dao, with the Three Clarities (Sanqing 三清), the pre-eminent trinity of gods representing the Dao, the scriptures, and the masters, at the top of the pantheon. Yet the Dao is also represented by Taishang Laojun 太上老君, the deified Laozi, alone who is also worshiped as a single deity (outside the trinity of the Sanqing, where he occupies the third position as Daode Tianzun 道德天尊) on Mt. Laojun and in many other Daoist sanctuaries.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: This pertains to some Daoist deities, e.g., the divinities of the sun and the moon, and those connected to the Dipper constellations.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: While the Daoist high gods are not chthonic, there do exist lower levels of spiritual forces connected to the underworld.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Notes: There were certain exceptions in Chinese history. For example, the imperial family of the Tang dynasty (618-907) regarded Laozi as their ancestor, and Daoism enjoyed governmental sponsorship on a grand scale, but this was not a continuum in the history of Daoism.

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

Notes: From the late Qing dynasty to 1949, Mt. Laojun was managed by the local Liumen community. Liu Yuan, founder and first patriarch of Liumen, had a Daoist master, who stayed with him on Mt. Laojun. This master is said to be an incarnation of Laozi. Thus, Liu Yuan had a direct connection to Laozi, and Liu was worshiped in the Rulin Ci shrine on Mt. Laojun, which was demolished only recently.

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– I don't know

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– I don't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– I don't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue visible:

– Yes

↳ Is the cult statue hidden:

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– Yes

Notes: The standard Daoist Five Offerings (wugong 五供) comprise incense, flowers, an oil lamp, water, and fruit. Incense, candles, and sacrificial paper money are presented daily by the Daoists and lay believers.

↳ Libations:

– Yes [specify]: Water, tea, liquor (according to the status of deities and the ritual occasion).

↳ Offerings of food:

– Yes [specify]: Fruits and vegetarian food are standard; however, on certain occasions martial and chthonic deities may receive meat offerings.

↳ Animal sacrifice:

– No

↳ Human sacrifice:

– No

↳ Sacred objects:

– I don't know

↳ Daily life objects:

– I don't know

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– Yes

↳ Other:

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Notes: Blood and animal sacrifices have always been part of Chinese popular religion, but Daoism has opposed these practices since its very beginnings as an organized religion. Therefore, items "sacrificed" during Daoist liturgy are mostly limited to incense, flowers, ritual paper money, fruit and vegetarian food, candles, water, tea, liquor, and a variety of written ritual documents which are burned.

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– No

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: The standard Daoist Five Offerings (wugong 五供) comprise incense, flowers, an oil lamp, water, and fruit. Incense, candles, and sacrificial paper money are presented daily by the Daoists and lay believers.

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

Notes: Only during special rituals or to be sealed in new statues, may jewelry or precious cloth be among the offerings, but these are rarely used. Sacrificial items during ritual are mostly of a highly symbolic nature, e.g., valuable objects offered during funerary rites are replaced by paper effigies.

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Paper effigies of daily-life objects and large amounts of sacrificial money are burned during funerary rites.

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: I don't know.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Notes: Apart from recurring large-scale religious festivals, the resident Daoists are required to participate in daily morning and evening scripture-recitation liturgies (zao/wan gongke 早晚功課).

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: The resident Daoists (monks and nuns).

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: Many lay adherents work for the temple on a daily basis and also live there. However, for repairs and construction work, professional workers are hired.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Cleaning of the temple halls and a certain amount of physical labor are an integral part of Daoist practice.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: I am unaware of organized pilgrimages connected to Mt. Laojun, at least in the present day. Local worshipers and visitors climb the mountain every day, with many burning incense in the

temple or consulting the divination sticks. It appears that very large numbers of worshipers visit the Laozi Temple during its liturgical festivals, in particular Laozi's birthday in the second lunar month. It is likely that worshipers were organized in pilgrimage associations (xianghui 香會) before 1949, but I have no proof of this still being the case in the present.

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: As to the religious festivals of Mt. Laojun, we only have access to data from the modern era (late Qing dynasty to the present). It is likely that the festivals followed the liturgical calendar of the Liumen community who managed the Laozi temple before 1949. However, the birthday of Laozi in the second month of the traditional calendar is the main religious festival and seems to have a long history. After reopening the temple in the second half of the 1980s, Quanzhen Daoists of the Longmen (Dragon Gate) lineage took over its management, and the liturgical calendar was also reshaped by them, following the tradition of Sichuanese Quanzhen Daoism. On the role of the Liumen community, see my article "The Gazetteer of Mt. Tianshe – How the Liumen Community Reshaped a Daoist Sacred Mountain," in: PHILIP CLART (ed.). *Chinese and European Perspectives on the Study of Chinese Popular Religions*. Taipei: Boyang wenhua, 2012, pp. 229–263 (PDF attached under "Contextual Media/Files). On the details of the festival calendar of Mt. Laojun, see the tables and pictures attached here.

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– All members

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– Yes

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Varies with the occasion; from several dozen during minor liturgies to tens of thousands during the celebration of Laozi's Birthday. (pre-pandemic times)

- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
 - Notes: Collectively enjoying a vegetarian meal is an essential part of any Chinese temple festival.

- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

- Yes

- ↳ Divination by examination of the exta:
 - Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species

- No

- ↳ Divination through human communication:

- Yes

- ↳ Is a human being the vehicle for the oracle:

- No

- ↳ Is a human being the interpreter of the oracle:

- Yes

- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified sex/gender:

- No

- ↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified ethnicity:

– No

↳ Are the oracle interpreters of a specified class:

– Yes

Notes: As a rule, resident Daoists (mostly monks) will explain the meaning of divination texts to inquirers.

↳ Is sex-deprivation required:

– No

↳ Are intoxicants required:

– No

↳ Physical ordeal required:

– No

↳ Divination through animal-behavior:

– No

↳ Divination through non-living material:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: The most common form of divination in Chinese temples is using divination sticks made of bamboo, which are stored in a wooden tube. The latter is shaken by the inquirer in front of the altar until a single stick falls out of the tube. The number on the stick refers to a corresponding divination poem which is generally explained by a resident cleric. This method is also used in the Laozi Temple on Mt. Laojun.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: I don't know.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– No

↳ Healing magic

– Yes

Notes: Healing may be sought through ritual means, which may involve the participation in a large-scale liturgy (and the submission of a ritual petition) or the purchase of a relevant talisman (fu 符) etc.

↳ Cleansing

– Yes

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– Yes

Notes: Moral self-reform and vows to perform good deeds etc. are expected from all participants in Daoist rituals. This can be seen as a continuation of the idea of healing through repentance in early Daoism.

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Many Daoists are practitioners of traditional Chinese medicine, some of them even experts, and they treat patients on a regular basis.

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: Daoist rituals are extremely complex in nature; single rituals are combined to fill the program of large-scale liturgical festivals that can last several days or even a week and longer. Before 1949, since the Liumen community managed the Laozi Temple, rituals were certainly performed by priests of the Liumen-derived Fayan tan 法言壇 lineage. After reopening the temple as a religious institution in the late 1980s, the liturgy of the Guangcheng tan 廣成壇 tradition, which is connected to local Quanzhen Daoism and has now become the mainstream of Daoist liturgy in Sichuan, became the standard of the temple's ritual repertoire. However, in the early 1990s, Fayan tan priests still performed rituals during the Middle Prime (Zhongyuan) festival, but the collaboration of the Quanzhen Daoists now managing the temple with the Liumen tradition and their Fayan tan lineage has unfortunately not been continued.

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: See above under "Festivals".

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: See above under "Festivals".

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Notes: Mt. Laojun is a sacred site of Daoism with a long history. However, nothing is known about the Daoists who managed the temple prior to the modern and contemporary era. The Longmen 龍門 (Dragon Gate) branch of Quanzhen 全真 (Complete Perfection) Daoism spread rapidly across the area of Sichuan during the Kangxi 康熙 reign (1662-1722) of the Qing dynasty, and the majority of Daoist temples in this region came under the management of Longmen masters. It is possible that the sanctuary on Mt. Laojun also became a part of the Longmen domain at that time, but there is no written evidence for that. In the late Qing dynasty and Republican times (1912-1949), the temple on Mt. Laojun was managed by local members of the Liumen 劉門 tradition (see my article "The Gazetteer of Mt. Tianshe – How the Liumen Community Reshaped a Daoist Sacred Mountain" under "Contextual Media/Files") who rebuilt the sanctuary after a devastating fire in 1923, with the architectural ensemble modelled on the famous Daoist temple Qingyang gong 青羊宮 (Palace of the Grey Ram) in Chengdu, which was also patronized by the Liumen community. After the founding of the People's Republic of China (1949), the Liumen movement was outlawed as a "reactionary secret society," and Mt. Laojun was consequently deprived of its former protectors. After the turmoil of the "Cultural Revolution" (1966-1976), the temple was finally reopened as a religious institution in 1986. In 1988, the Quanzhen Daoist abbess Zhang Zhirong 張至容, who was trained on the nearby Daoist sacred mountain Qingcheng Shan 青城山, took over the management of the temple on Mt. Laojun, which hereby officially became a

monastery of the Longmen branch of Quanzhen Daoism. In 1989, the state-controlled Daoist Association of Xinjin District 新津縣道教協會 was established, headed by abbess Zhang Zhirong. The temple was successfully revived as a Daoist sanctuary with a thriving monastic community and rich liturgical activities. However, the cultural heritage of the Liumen community, which is still very visible through precious inscriptions and artefacts, is not acknowledged on the official side. The Rulin Ci 儒林祠 shrine once dedicated to Liumen founder Liu Yuan was destroyed in 2022 and replaced by a modern Fangzhang Yuan 方丈院 (Grand-Abbess Chamber). The planned promotion of abbess Zhang to fangzhang 方丈 ("grand-abbess") brought about efforts to "standardize" the temple complex on Mt. Laojun, which is best understood as another effort of the state-controlled religious administration to "guide" Daoism's development and to rewrite its history.

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– No

Notes: Not as a rule. However, most Daoists definitely belong to the Han majority among the Chinese ethnicities.

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– No

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– No

Notes: While lifelong dedication is an option, today's Daoists are characterized by a great mobility, especially the younger generation.

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The state-controlled Daoist Association of Xinjin District is headquartered on Mt. Laojun.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

Notes: The state-controlled Daoist Association of Xinjin District is headquartered on Mt. Laojun.

Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– No

Notes: Without in-depth knowledge of Mt. Laojun's financial situation, I suppose that regular contributions by wealthy lay adherents and ritual fees constitute a major source of income. While the temple never sold entrance tickets to visitors, thus being a rare exception among Chinese religious sites, the Daoists run a restaurant, a teahouse, and several shops on the mountain. However, these sources of income have been severely affected by the Covid pandemic, in particular by the strict "zero-Covid" policy of the government, leading to a series of lockdowns of the temple and the long-term closure of the tourist facilities.

Does this place lease out land:

– I don't know

↳ Does this place lease out tools:

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: In Republican times, the Laozi Temple was used as a base for the Liumen community's local charity work, including the distribution of food or money to the poor, medical treatment, the supply of coffins or burial places to needy families, and ritual services. This charitable institution ceased to exist after 1949. Today's Daoist Association also participates in charitable activities, and Mt. Laojun itself continues to be a very popular place for the people of Xinjin who engage in various social activities while visiting the mountain and its temple.

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that all records (except inscriptions on stone steles) of the Laozi Temple dating from the period before 1949 have been destroyed. Therefore, what is stored there now only reflects a very short episode of Mt. Laojun's history.

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: Mt. Laojun is listed in several works of the Daoist Canon and historical treatises on geography as well as local gazetteers of Xinjin district. A short description of the mountain and its history titled *Tianshe shan zhi* 天社山志 (Gazetteer of Mt. Tianshe) was authored by an adherent of the Liumen community in the second half of the 20th century. However, none of these accounts can be defined as a "scripture".